

LESLLA Symposium Proceedings

Recommended citation of this article

DeCapua, A., & Marshall, H. W. (2015). Implementing a Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm in a Community-Based Adult ESL Literacy Class. *LESLLA Symposium Proceedings*, 9(1), 151–171. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8022534>

Citation for LESLLA Symposium Proceedings

This article is part of a collection of articles based on presentations from the 2013 Symposium held at City College of San Francisco, San Francisco, California, USA. Please note that the year of publication is often different than the year the symposium was held. We recommend the following citation when referencing the edited collection.

Santos, M. G., & Whiteside, A. (Eds.) (2015). *Low-educated second language and literacy acquisition (LESLLA): Proceedings of the 9th symposium*. Lulu Publishing Services. <https://lesllasp.journals.publicknowledgeproject.org/index.php/lesllasp/issue/view/474>

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Implementing a Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm in a Community-Based Adult ESL Literacy Class

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Abstract

This study examined the engagement of one teacher with the Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm (MALP) in community adult basic education ESL literacy programs and her development as she implemented this model in a community-based adult language and literacy program for Haitians. We adopt a qualitative methodology to study teacher practices consistent with this model, which is designed to transition learners with little, interrupted, or no formal education to Western-style formal education and literacy practices. We examine how, using MALP, the teacher was able to encourage active participation, develop a sense of community, and reduce the cultural dissonance (Ibarra, 2001) that students were experiencing. Our results describe how these practices led to increased engagement in and ownership of learning and greater self-confidence. We conclude the study with an examination of the difficulties of doing research with immigrant adults in community-based organizations and a consideration of the importance of continuing to conduct such research despite the barriers.

Introduction

The extent of prior exposure to Western-style formal education varies greatly among ESL students. Those familiar and comfortable with the expectations of such education are likely to progress satisfactorily. In contrast, emerging empirical research indicates that students new to formal education learn languages, become print literate, and engage with school differently, which points to the need for alternative pedagogical approaches (e.g., Bigelow, 2010; DeCapua & Marshall, 2011; Marshall & DeCapua, 2013; Peyton, 2012; Young-Scholten, 2007). Here, we follow an ESL literacy teacher as she engages Haitian adult learners in an innovative approach designed to transition them to formal education and increase their comfort level with school-based learning processes and activities. Together, they forge a learning community that succeeds in moving students toward a new level of confidence and achievement, where literacy practices are centered around their needs, interests, and lived experiences to empower them in their lives (Freire, 1994).

Different Ways of Teaching and Learning

Western-style formal education is equated with formal classroom settings, trained teachers, standard curricula, and specific classroom behaviors and ways of thinking. Although this style of formal education has cultural variations around the world (Anderson-Levitt, 2003; Grigorenko, 2007), the underlying assumptions remain the same. Students are expected to engage in ways of thinking and learning derived from systematic, logical, and controlled ways of examining and understanding the world—ways that have their basis in scientific thought (Flynn, 2007; Ozmon & Carver, 2008). Much of this learning has no direct application to life in the real world or any immediate relevance because learning is future-oriented, whether as a foundation for a more advanced course, preparation for a test, or simply for the sake of learning (Bruner, 1961; Crumpton & Gregory, 2011). Strong literacy skills are central in the learning and teaching process, and students are

held individually accountable for their work, which is manifested most commonly on tests. This is the learning paradigm with which U.S. educators are familiar and comfortable (DeCapua & Marshall, 2011; Marshall & DeCapua, 2013).

Many low-educated ESL students, however, come from a different learning paradigm, that is, informal ways of learning. Learning is not separated and compartmentalized from daily life as in formal schooling, but it takes place as part of the sociocultural practices of a community (Paradise & Rogoff, 2009; Silva, Correa-Chávez, & Rogoff, 2010). It is immediately relevant learning that occurs when necessary; this learning focuses on the tasks, endeavors, skills, procedures, and rituals that comprise daily life. Teaching and learning consist of modeling, demonstration, imitation, and practice to gain mastery (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Paradise & Rogoff, 2009). Literacy is neither central nor necessary, even. This is the learning paradigm that many low-educated ESL students find familiar and comfortable (DeCapua & Marshall, 2011; Marshall & DeCapua, 2013).

We emphasize that these two paradigms do not represent neat dichotomies but provide a means for clarifying differences between distinct approaches to teaching and learning. Just as not all students in Western-style formal education systems demonstrate the same degree of mastery, so, too, will low-educated ESL students fall all along the continuum of ways of teaching and learning (DeCapua & Marshall, 2011; Marshall & DeCapua, 2013). At the farthest end of the continuum, away from formal education, are students who are primarily or exclusively oral. They come to U.S. classrooms with no or very limited literacy skills, both in their native language and in English, and with zero or little exposure to formal Western-style schooling. Others come with more developed literacy skills and have some content background; still others approach expected literacy and content knowledge, but are still used to nonschool-based, decontextualized ways of thinking. What all of these low-educated learners share is their being accustomed to engaging in different cognitive processes shaped by culturally influenced learning experiences that are distinctive from those that are the norm

in formal classroom settings (Cole, 2005; Gauvain, Beebe, & Zhao, 2011; Silva et al., 2010). Students finding themselves in such settings must master decontextualized school tasks removed from the context of sociocultural practices, and also develop their literacy skills and content and/or vocational knowledge. Thus, we argue that the focus for instructors must be threefold: literacy, content knowledge, *and* new ways of thinking. It is this third factor that few educators are aware of, because it derives from hidden cultural factors. Yet it is these new ways of thinking that must be explicitly taught.

To accomplish this, DeCapua and Marshall (2010a; 2010b; 2011) and Marshall and DeCapua (2013) suggest that teachers of low-educated ESL students implement the Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm. The struggles faced by these students often stem from *cultural dissonance* (Ibarra, 2001) because they generally do not share the assumptions about teaching and learning prevalent in formal school settings and find themselves confounded by the ways in which language and content are presented, practiced, and assessed. These underlying cultural differences must be made explicit to educators so that they can develop effective strategies to address the needs of this population. It is essential that educators understand how *cultural* values, beliefs, and practices influence *educational* beliefs and practices (DeCapua & Wintergerst, 2004). To address the cultural dissonance described above, DeCapua and Marshall (2011) and Marshall and DeCapua (2013) developed an instructional model, the Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm, which is designed to transition students to formal school settings through a mutually adaptive approach. In MALP, the priorities of both learners and the formal educational setting are taken *equally* into account, thereby reducing the cultural dissonance these students experience in formal classroom settings. Literacy and learning must be relevant and built around their needs, interests, and daily lives.

Implementation of MALP promotes academic achievement for low-educated ESL students by: (1) accepting the conditions students need to learn; (2) combining the processes for learning essential for them with those that are key to learning in U.S. classrooms; and (3)

engaging students in school-based ways of thinking and performing decontextualized tasks, initially scaffolded by the use of familiar language and content.

Accepting conditions for learning necessitates teachers' adapting to learners' needs by ensuring that lessons have immediate relevance and are not simply provided as a means to reach some future end point. It also entails teachers' personal investment in making meaningful connections with learners, along with promoting strong bonds among learners to form an interconnected web of relationships.

Combining processes for learning asks both teachers and learners to adapt their learning paradigms. Learners transition from their preference for relying on the oral mode and on fellow students for constant support during learning. Teachers reach across to the learners' paradigm by including oral elements combined with the written word and sharing responsibility, along with tasks requiring individual accountability.

Focusing on new activities for learning involves students' adapting to formal educational expectations by developing new ways of thinking. Teachers ensure that new school-based tasks are accessible by introducing them with material familiar to learners and using language that learners have encountered previously.

Finally, teachers must develop effective instruction, that is, present content and develop literacy and school skills so that these are accessible to their students. This does not mean dumbing or watering down the curriculum, but it entails presenting and practicing literacy, content, and school ways of thinking by culturally scaffolding them with culturally responsive teaching, which incorporates the diverse funds of knowledge, heritage, experience, and student perspective into the curriculum and the classroom (Gauvain et al., 2011; Gay, 2002; González et al., 2005).

The Study

The study took place in a Haitian community-based organization (CBO) located in an urban-suburban area near the New York City

metropolitan area. This CBO, which has little external funding, is run almost exclusively by volunteers. The organization provides training in a variety of family and social services, acts as social center for the local Haitian community, and offers various entry-level courses. There is high demand for literacy and ESL classes, but resources are limited. Classes are offered for free, running whenever the CBO has available teachers—often volunteers without any pedagogical training, which is problematic. At the time of the study, a teacher had resigned suddenly, and a graduate student from the TESOL program of one of the researchers agreed to step in to teach and assist the researchers in a study of the implementation of the MALP model in this type of setting.

Method

Data Collection

Data were qualitative and gathered over a five-month period through (1) an informal intake assessment; (2) classroom observations by the researchers and by a fellow graduate student of the volunteer teacher; and (3) the completion of MALP checklists (see Table 1 in Appendix) by the researchers and the graduate students.

Intake assessment. New students were given a short questionnaire asking about their age, time in the United States, prior schooling, and English proficiency. When available, the community liaison, or another volunteer, assisted. At other times, the class assistant or one of the researchers administered the questionnaire with help from more-proficient students. However, with new students coming in at any point, even during a lesson, it was not always possible to do this.

Classroom observations. The two researchers took turns observing the class and taking extensive field notes using the MALP checklist. At times, they engaged in participant observation where they were actively involved in interacting with students and participating in the

day's lesson. On other occasions, they disengaged from the class, merely observing and recording class dynamics. For the last three months, a graduate student also assisted in and observed the classes, using the MALP checklist.

MALP checklist. To ensure full and effective implementation of the MALP instructional model, DeCapua and Marshall (2011) and Marshall and DeCapua (2013) developed the MALP Teacher Planning Checklist (see Appendix A). Teachers use the checklist in planning to ensure that they are fully incorporating the model, and they use it again after their lessons to review areas of strength and weakness. The checklist is also valuable to observers for assessing classroom execution of MALP. In the present study, the teacher, the researchers, and the graduate student who observed completed checklists (see Appendix A for a sample).

Participant Population

The teacher and the assistant. The teacher, Katie (not a pseudonym), already a certified elementary and special education teacher, was now completing a master's degree in TESOL and had received MALP training. Erika (a pseudonym), a fellow graduate student who was also a certified classroom teacher and familiar with MALP, regularly helped Katie and acted as another observer.

The students. The director, himself a Haitian immigrant, was intimately connected to the community and able to provide valuable insights into the students taking the ESL/literacy class. The students were all Haitian, ranging in age from 16 to 77, although the majority of students were in their midtwenties to early forties. They were Creole speakers with little knowledge of French. Their native language literacy skills ranged from alphabet recognition to being able to write basic sentences, and they had had anywhere between two and 14 years of schooling in Haiti. The students had been in the United States anywhere from three

months to seven years, and their oral English proficiency varied from low to advanced beginner. Class size ranged from 18 to 27 students, almost all female. The participants were not consistently the same, as Katie was working with a large number of constantly rotating students.

The intervention. The study took place over the course of five months. Initially, classes met twice weekly for two hours, changing after the first two months to once weekly due to Katie's course load.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Here, we examine two lessons, one from early in the intervention and one toward the end. In each case, there is a description of the lesson and an analysis of the elements of MALP using the MALP checklist.

Lesson no. 1 description (week 3). In creating her lessons, Katie thoughtfully considered topics that would resonate with her students. One evening, she came with a bad cold and used this as the basis for a lesson on illness. Katie showed the students photos of people sneezing, coughing, and holding their throat. Pointing to each photo, she asked, "What is wrong?" Some pictures elicited one-word responses or students' demonstrating what they saw.

Katie was careful to write down each word that her students produced. Some words and phrases, such as *headache* and *sore throat*, proved difficult to pronounce, so, for example, she worked with the students on the initial *h* and the initial cluster, *θr*. In addition, Katie pointed out the morphology of compound nouns, such as *headache*, *toothache*, *stomachache*, and *earache*, so that the students could appreciate the commonality with the word *ache*.

Next, with Katie's guidance and prompting, the class constructed sentences for each photo, such as, "I have a sore throat," which Katie wrote on the board. Students composed sentences and practiced changing the sentences to third person, as in, "She has a sore throat." Finally, Katie gave the students time to copy sentences from the board.

Lesson no. 1 analysis. Undoubtedly, Katie was considering the MALP model in this lesson. By selecting illness as the topic when she herself was ill, she was both making the lesson immediately relevant and increasing her interconnectedness with the class. As the students and Katie shared their experiences with illnesses, they also increased the level of their openness with each other. Katie clearly accepted the students' conditions for learning.

Regarding the processes for learning, Katie consistently used both oral and written forms of all language introduced and practiced. She took dictation as students participated orally (*speaking*). She wrote their sentences on the board, editing as needed (*reading*). She read the sentences first herself (*listening*) and then along with the student(s). Students then shared their sentences with their classmates without reading from the board (*speaking*). Finally, the students copied their sentences into their notebooks (*writing*). However, because the students preferred the oral mode, they focused more on their pronunciation than on their writing, which consisted entirely of copying from the board once the vocabulary word or sentence had been written on it.

Katie incorporated shared responsibility by allowing students to help each other with pronunciation and with remembering their sentences, and allowing them to provide each other with cues in Haitian Creole. Nevertheless, although Katie attempted to hold students individually accountable for their oral participation and for writing down the sentences they had created, there was some resistance, particularly from the less proficient and/or less literate students in the group. Moreover, as Erika stressed in her checklist, not every student had an opportunity to participate as an individual. Overall, Katie still needed to work on transitioning the students to the less familiar and less comfortable processes for learning: using the written mode and demonstrating individual accountability.

Finally, as indicated in the MALP model, there must be a focus on new activities to support the development of new ways of thinking. In this case, the learning activities themselves were essentially familiar tasks of repeating, copying, and recombining words to make sentences.

Katie was not requiring academic tasks to build facility with unfamiliar ways of thinking. Vocabulary related to illness is familiar content in the sense that all human beings have been sick at one time or another. Katie noted in her reflection on this lesson that it is necessary for students to be able to respond when asked how they are feeling. While this is no doubt the case, the focus of her teaching was exclusively on English language development. Katie clearly had much to offer her students regarding phonology, morphology, and syntax. Yet, in this and in the subsequent lessons which were similar, Katie remained focused on language, not moving the students toward decontextualized, school-based tasks as called for in MALP.

Lesson no. 2 description (week 18). We now turn to another lesson, nearly four months later, after Katie had been coached and debriefed weekly by the researchers. The purpose of this lesson was to introduce the academic tasks of categorizing and sorting, using a relevant topic: familiar stores where the students lived.

Katie began the lesson by showing photos of area stores and asking the students to identify them. This led to conversation about differences between supermarkets, department stores, and superstores. Katie and the students together created a graphic organizer to categorize each of the stores provided by the students. Referring to the T-chart, the class reviewed the types of products they could purchase at both supermarkets and department stores. Using this information, Katie showed additional photos of other stores and asked the class to decide whether the photo belonged on the chart labeled “supermarkets” or on the chart labeled “department stores.” She also had advertisement circulars from stores and showed the students pictures of the products inside these circulars to help them to make a connection between the visual representations and the written words on the board. Katie’s final task was for the students to write one sentence using a product from the circulars to say what they wanted for Christmas or what they had already bought for themselves or a family member. To assist them, Katie provided the sentence frame on the board.

Lesson no. 2 analysis. This lesson represented Katie's development as a MALP instructor. In her notes, Erika commented that she had witnessed all elements of MALP being successfully incorporated into the lesson. Our analysis of the data on this lesson confirms the conclusion from Katie's peer observer.

The lesson was immediately relevant because it involved real stores in the area that the students had seen and had frequently shopped in. Katie and the students developed and maintained interconnectedness by sharing shopping experiences at these stores.

Regarding combining processes for learning, Katie was much more effective than in earlier lessons. The students continued to assist each other throughout the lesson by speaking in Creole to clarify vocabulary and ideas. They also individually shared examples of times they went to specific stores and things they bought there. Katie wrote everything they said on the board. The process of oral communication to printed word was reinforced by having students read the sentence or words aloud after Katie wrote them. Later, the students were asked to independently write a sentence describing an item they had bought or wanted to buy from their store of choice.

Most importantly, the component of MALP that had earlier eluded Katie was clearly present in this lesson. She focused on academic ways of thinking and on decontextualized, school-based tasks. She asked students to categorize each store as either a supermarket, a department store, or a superstore, introducing an academic way of thinking, i.e., categorization. All tasks were created and performed using student-provided language. The basic sentence patterns Katie used were familiar, and the vocabulary had been generated by the students during previous lessons. The content was also familiar, as the students all went shopping regularly and knew the stores and store products.

Overall Analysis of MALP Implementation

In analyzing the checklists completed by the researchers and the peer observer, the following themes emerged.

Katie was cognizant of the elements of MALP, yet it took her until well into the intervention to be able to implement the model fully. The easiest component of the model for Katie was to accept the conditions for learning. All of her lessons were driven by immediate relevance. There was no prescribed curriculum or prescribed materials. Katie could elicit topics from students and use whatever material spontaneously emerged, such as the lesson on illnesses. That lesson sprang from her own illness, and she used it to involve the students in exploring ways to express themselves in English.

The other condition, interconnectedness, manifested itself naturally, as the students were all members of a close-knit local Haitian immigrant community. Katie's focus was on having them deepen their connections, as well as on establishing a strong relationship with them. This she did by having the students share family photos and important personal dates such as birthdays, and by encouraging them to share personal examples for each of her lesson topics.

Somewhat more perplexing for Katie were the processes for learning. The students were much more comfortable with oral transmission and shared responsibility. They became nervous when they had to write or speak on their own without help. Katie struggled to create situations wherein they would naturally transition into the new behaviors, but their resistance frequently thwarted her. Initially, writing remained as copying, not generating print. Speaking or reading aloud from the board remained as repeating after the teacher or being prompted by fellow students. However, in the later part of the intervention, Katie did gradually succeed at moving many students along in terms of these new processes.

Finally, it was the academic tasks, the new activities for learning, which eluded Katie until the very last class sessions. Until that point, she, as an ESL teacher, was focusing primarily on language instruction. The lessons were about vocabulary—for holidays, for food, for illnesses, and so on—or about grammar, including past tense, subject-verb agreement, etc. Furthermore, these were traditional ESL lessons in terms of the activities Katie conducted insofar as they consisted of familiar ways

of students' practicing what they were learning, such as watching the teacher model, repeating after her, or copying. During debriefings, the researchers emphasized that these were not new academic tasks and did not serve to introduce the students to academic ways of thinking. Subsequently, Katie went on to create a series of lessons in which the students had to identify, discuss, and, finally, categorize types of stores. It was in these lessons that Katie succeeded in introducing academic ways of thinking by using familiar language and content.

Summary of Findings

It is unrealistic to expect low-educated ESL students to engage immediately in the cognitive practices of schooling to which they have limited or no exposure or with which they have limited practice. MALP helps transition this population, in that teachers accommodate students' priorities and, at the same time, prepare them to engage in the standard and essential practices of schooling: accessing and transmitting information via print (literacy); taking individual responsibility (grades and testing); and employing academic ways of thinking (decontextualized tasks).

The data analysis indicates that Katie was ultimately successful in implementing MALP. During each lesson, Katie used various techniques to ensure that the material was immediately relevant to the students. The topics Katie selected evolved naturally from the students' own interests. She based all lessons on these interests, keeping in mind their literacy and language needs and proficiency. This also allowed Katie to promote the interconnectedness that is so important to these Haitian students. In her completed checklists and debriefing sessions, Katie noted how much more engaged the students had become over the five-month period and how much more willing they were to move beyond copying and recitation. It was gratifying to Katie to see how those students who consistently attended her classes worked with newly arrived students to encourage them in the "new" style of teaching.

Throughout each step of her lesson, Katie explicitly connected the oral and the written. In traditional ESL pedagogy, four skills are usually distinguished: speaking, listening, reading, and writing. Oral production is viewed as separate from reading; however, in MALP, making explicit connections between oral transmission and print is essential. When students orally responded to Katie, she immediately wrote what they said. Pointing to each word and/or phrase, she had the students read the information back to her individually and/or chorally. While many of the students gravitated toward the oral and away from the written, Katie gradually moved them closer to using print and away from relying solely on oral modes.

Haitians, as members of a very collectivistic culture, prefer being with others, working with others, and interacting with others (James, Noel, Favorite, & Jean, 2012). Katie was conscientious in encouraging students to work both together and individually. Since individual accountability is expected in U.S. schools, the MALP model, as a transitional model, requires that opportunities for both group work and individual work be incorporated in lessons. Here again, there was initial resistance to individual participation, which Katie overcame as time passed and students became more relaxed and confident, as well as more proficient.

These students were used to informal ways of learning and to pragmatic tasks. They were accustomed to learning what they needed to learn as circumstances required, generally by watching and doing rather than by engaging in school-based ways of interacting, thinking, and receiving and processing information. For many, the goal was to eventually be able to find jobs beyond the most menial ones, which most of them held, given their limited literacy, lack of English proficiency, and, as we have argued, unfamiliarity with school-based, decontextualized ways of thinking. Although we realize that MALP is not a panacea for the numerous societal obstacles that low-educated immigrants face, we believe that accessing language, literacy, and formal ways of thinking will make a difference in their ability to navigate these obstacles. Katie, by including tasks derived from this type of thinking, was helping them

learn to think in new ways, using familiar language and content so that the focus was exclusively on the task when the task itself was the focus. Her struggles and eventual success in helping the students (categorize) validated, from our point of view, the necessity of introducing classroom ways of thinking by using familiar language and content.

In addition to the data gathered from the observations, both by Katie's fellow graduate student and by the researchers, there was positive anecdotal evidence pointing to the effectiveness of the MALP intervention. At every class, new students arrived; the class mushroomed from a handful of students to nearly 30 on a typical night. Through word of mouth, these students heard about Katie's class and wanted to become a part of the positive learning experience she was creating. The director also indicated to Katie, both at the time and in subsequent months after the intervention, that the students found the class to be quite different from anything they had experienced before and that they very much wanted her to continue and, later, return.

Limitations of the Study

The exploratory findings need to be considered in light of several limitations. The plan for the study included intake and outtake assessments. Although in many cases it was possible to collect intake assessment data, it was not possible to do any outtake assessments, due to the nature of the program. Because the CBO operated with an open enrollment policy, students could join the class whenever they wanted or when they learned about it. Moreover, they attended whenever they could, which meant that there was a lack of consistent attendance over the course of the entire intervention.

Another limitation of the study is that there was only one teacher. Results may differ when more than one teacher is involved: Are the findings justifiably the result of the implementation of the MALP model, or are there personality, professionalism, or other characteristics of the teacher in question at play? With only one teacher participating in the study, it is difficult to draw the conclusion that MALP alone made

the difference. Nevertheless, the literature indicates a richness of data and a breadth of qualitative research, which is lacking in quantitative studies and which can significantly contribute to our understanding of pedagogy and classroom practices (Cresswell, 2012; Maxwell, 2012). Here, for example, through a qualitative approach, the researchers gained valuable insights into Katie's developing ability to implement MALP over the course of the study. Furthermore, this approach gave Katie a voice to reflect on experiences and record her thoughts about the implementation and her growing familiarity and comfort with it in her teaching.

The nature of CBOs is another issue that impacted this research. There are many different types of CBOs. Some of these receive significant and consistent funding and support, are highly structured, have paid staff, and offer a variety of formal support services, including language and literacy classes. However, many others, like the Haitian one described here, are more informal, receive little consistent funding, and are consequently more loosely structured, with their services depending on what the current funding will support and what the volunteers can offer. The classes at such a CBO will be less consistent and will frequently offer open enrollment. In terms of conducting a controlled research study, open enrollment and the concomitant lack of consistent attendance over the time frame of an intervention make collecting data and drawing valid conclusions difficult.

Difficulties of implementing studies in CBOs. The diverse types of CBOs, with their varied foci and institutional structures, present both opportunities and challenges for researchers. While these factors are somewhat different from those that are present in K–12 settings, there are similarities between the two. For example, Marshall, DeCapua, and Antolini (2010) found in the research on high school students who had limited or interrupted formal education that inconsistent attendance, a major problem in the current study, was also an issue.

On the other hand, unlike most CBOs, teachers in K–12 public school settings are certified and have appropriate pedagogical training,

although the latter is often not the case with ESL populations, especially low-educated learners (Darling-Hammond, 2012). Nevertheless, the fact remains that public schools are not “drop-in institutions”; they are highly structured and formally organized in ways that many CBOs, such as the Haitian one, are not.

From this brief discussion, the question arises as to whether or not research should (or can) be conducted in CBOs. We argue here that low-educated adult ESL learners are an understudied population that deserves to be researched in order to better serve them. Despite the difficulties of conducting such research, employing qualitative methods of data can provide insights and direction. In this study, the use of the MALP checklist by all the vested parties, and the subsequent analysis of these by the two researchers, along with debriefings, provided rich sources of data regarding the development of Katie’s full implementation of the MALP instructional model. It is important that other researchers replicate and extend our study with the expectation that the promising findings of the current study will lead to progressively more extensive implementation of MALP.

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank Kathryn Mercury, a graduate of Long Island University – Hudson’s TESOL Program, for her active involvement in this project and for graciously allowing us to observe her classes.

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Appendix: Teacher Planning Checklist

Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm™ – MALP™	
Teacher Planning Checklist	
A. Accept Conditions for Learning	
A1. I am making this lesson/project immediately relevant to my students.	<input type="checkbox"/>
A2. I am helping students develop and maintain interconnectedness.	<input type="checkbox"/>
B. Combine Processes for Learning	
B1. I am incorporating both shared responsibility and individual accountability.	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2. I am scaffolding the written word through oral interaction.	<input type="checkbox"/>
C. Focus on New Activities for Learning	
C1. I am focusing on tasks requiring academic ways of thinking.	<input type="checkbox"/>
C2. I am making these tasks accessible with familiar language and content.	<input type="checkbox"/>